

Strain tuning MoO₃ vibrational and electronic properties

Supplementary Information

Supplementary Figure 1. Strain setup for angle-resolved uniaxial straining measurements (a) Sample transferred to the PC substrate, cut in a disc shape. (b) Picture of the three-points bending setup used for the strain engineering experiment. (c) scheme of the bending process in orthographic view, being L the length between the extreme rods, D the height difference from the initial position and t the thickness of the substrate used. (d, e) Representation of the sample upon uniaxial strain applied along one direction. In order to rotate the flake, the system, its direction is inspected under an optical microscope.

In order to obtain the maximum value of tensile strain we tested the *Sample 1*, studying the shift of the A_g^c Raman mode. Supplementary Figure 2 shows a deviation of the trend when the tensile strain is greater than 0.52%. Thus, we set the strain limit to 0.52% for the following samples, to not reach the slippage/breaking point during the experiments.

Supplementary Figure 2. Shift of the the A_g^c mode when a strain applied, showing a slippage/breaking point at 0.65, 0.78 and 1.17% of strain. Error bars showing standard deviation.

This behavior has been previously observed in our laboratory using other techniques, we refer the reader to the Figure 4 in the reference¹. This behavior is due to the breaking/slipping point has been reached, releasing the accumulated strain. Supplementary Figure 3, corresponding to Sample 6 in the present work, displays an optical comparison between the sample before, and after the strain measurements are carried out. In which cannot be observed more cracks than the ones that already are before taking the measurements, proving that the range we set is safe to not break the MoO₃ flakes.

Supplementary Figure 3. Optical images of the Sample 6 (a) before applying strain and, (b) after strain measurements. Length scale bar in (a) of 20 μm.

Supplementary Figure 4. Complete Raman spectra of the Figure 3 showing the 5 cycles of strain up to 0.52% applied along c -axis, note the shift of the peak A_g^c , pointed with a dashed line. A zoomed-in are of the A_g^a mode is displayed to show its negative shift.

Supplementary Figure 5. Complete Raman spectra of the Figure 3 showing the 5 cycles of strain up to 0.52% applied along a -axis, note the shift of the peak A_g^a , pointed with a dashed line.

Strain parallel to:			c -axis		a -axis	
Sample name	Target substrate	Thickness (nm)	A_g^c	A_g^a	A_g^c	A_g^a

Sample 3	SiO ₂	21	3.9 ± 0.4	-0.9 ± 0.4 (polar. // c)	---	4.7 ± 0.7
Sample 4	SiO ₂	19	3.7 ± 0.9	-0.9 ± 1.2 (polar. // c)	---	6.1 ± 1.5
Sample 5	SiO ₂	18	2.0 ± 0.6	-0.9 ± 0.5 (polar. // c)	---	4.5 ± 0.9
Sample 6	SiO ₂	20	5.3 ± 0.4	-0.5 ± 0.9 (polar. // a) -1.1 ± 0.4 (polar. // c)	2.3 ± 0.5 (polar. // c)	6.5 ± 0.5
Sample 7	SiO ₂	16	4.6 ± 0.6	-1.0 ± 0.6 (polar. // c)	---	5.2 ± 1.5
Sample 8	SiO ₂	16	2.4 ± 0.8	-1.7 ± 0.5 (polar. // c)	---	4.9 ± 1.0
Sample 12092023	mica	18	5.3 ± 1.2	0.7 ± 0.8 (polar. // a) 0.7 ± 0.9 (polar. // c)	1.6 ± 0.6 (polar. // c)	5.0 ± 0.7
Sample 18092023	mica	16	5.1 ± 0.9	0.4 ± 0.6 (polar. // a) -1.0 ± 1.7 (polar. // c)	1.4 ± 0.7 (polar. // c)	6.1 ± 1.0
Sample 03102023	mica	23	5.6 ± 0.9	-0.8 ± 0.4 (polar. // a) -0.9 ± 1.0 (polar. // c)	1.9 ± 0.7 (polar. // c)	5.4 ± 1.0

Supplementary Table 1. Summary of the samples tested using the Angle-resolved Raman spectroscopy when strain is applied. Includes the thickness of each sample, along with the RGF of the modes when the strain and the polarization of the laser are parallel to the c- and a-axes, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 6. AFM measurement of MoO_3 flake (Sample 3), placed on PC. Scale bar of 10 μm shown.

Supplementary Figure 7. RGF of the A_g^a mode along 100 cycles of strain.

sample name	axis	[I] (nA)	Thickness (nm)	Width (um)	[R] (GΩ)	[PGF]	\overline{PGF}
sample 11	c	±0.11	12	15	84-117	36-46	39±2
sample 14	c	±0.6	11	133	17-25	64-66	35±8
sample 28 (after cutting a-axis)	c	±15	12	33	0.65-0.86	37-39	38±1
sample 8	a	±0.4	16	39	24-29	23-28	26±2
sample 26	a	±18	10	101	0.6-0.7	34-40	38±3
sample 27	a	±10	16	20	1.1-1.4	23-30	27±1
sample 28 (before cutting a-axis)	a and c*	±10	12	89	1-1.3	46-47	46±2

Supplementary Table 2. Summary of device characteristics for all devices tested. List of tested samples with strain applied along the *c*, *a* and both axes in which, in each column it is specified the current range ([I]) of each device, the thickness of the MoO₃ film, its width connected to the Au electrodes, the electrical resistance ([R]) and the piezoresistive gauge factor ([PGF]) ranges, and the average calculated PGF with its uncertainty (\overline{PGF}). * The transferred film consisted of two domains with different crystal orientations.

Supplementary Figure 8. An optical picture of the Faraday cage utilized in the electrical measurements, used to minimize noise during the measurements. The connections of source, drain and ground are highlighted. Inside the automated strain setup is placed.

Supplementary Figure 9. PGF vs thickness of samples of MoO₃ grown on mica. Blue-star data points belong to samples connected to the electrodes along the *a*-axis, red-dotted data points along the *c*-axis and black-triangle to a sample connected along both directions. Error bars showing standard deviation.

Supplementary Figure 10. DFT calculations of the electrical resistance with the electron doping level for several values of compressive, negative, and tensile, positive strain along the two axes.

Electrical resistance calculated in the EPA and RTA approximations^{2,3} as a function of doping level obtained via the solution of the Boltzmann transport equation. The two results almost coincide for the range of doping levels considered here suggesting that the estimate of a constant relaxation time of 100 fs is accurate over a large range of energies.

Supplementary Figure 11. Electrical resistance calculated in the EPA and RTA approximations.

Supplementary References

1. Carrascoso, F., Frisenda, R. & Castellanos-Gomez, A. Biaxial versus uniaxial strain tuning of single-layer MoS₂. *Nano Materials Science* **4**, 44–51 (2022).
2. Samsonidze, G. & Kozinsky, B. Accelerated Screening of Thermoelectric Materials by First-Principles Computations of Electron–Phonon Scattering. *Adv Energy Mater* **8**, (2018).
3. Cepellotti, A., Coulter, J., Johansson, A., Fedorova, N. S. & Kozinsky, B. Phoebe: a high-performance framework for solving phonon and electron Boltzmann transport equations. *Journal of Physics: Materials* **5**, 035003 (2022).